

DAMAGE IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES UNDER TRANSVERSE LOADING

Hiroshi Suemasu¹, Yuichiro Aoki² and Takashi Ishikawa²

¹ *Department of Mechanical Engineering, Sophia University, Tokyo 102-8554, Japan*

² *National Aerospace Laboratory, Japan*

SUMMARY

An impact damage growth problem in composite laminates is numerically studied by simulating the growth of delaminations and transverse cracks during transverse loading. A three-dimensional interface element is introduced, where a deformation energy density function is defined as a function of relative displacements of the designated interface. The interlaminar toughness is chosen for the supremum value of the energy. The tractions are derived by differentiating the energy density function by the relating relative displacements. The element is incorporated in a commercially available finite element code by using the USER subroutine. A DCB and ENF fracture toughness test problems are analyzed to prove its validity. The solutions converge smoothly and the numerical results agree well with the theoretically predicted ones. Damage growth problem in cross-ply CFRP laminates subjected to transverse concentrated load is analyzed and is found that the delamination growth strongly depends on the damage growth sequence.

Keywords: multiple delaminations, interlaminar toughness, finite element analysis, cross-ply laminates

INTRODUCTION

Composite laminates are used particularly for aerospace structures due to their high specific strength and stiffness. However, structures made of composite laminates are vulnerable to transverse impact. The impact damages being difficult to be detected from outside may cause severe reduction of compressive strength (Compression After Impact: CAI)[1-2]. Design loads of the airplane structures are often limited by the degraded compressive performance. The mechanism of damage accumulation due to impact is required to be disclosed in order to utilize composite laminated structures to their full advantage.

There are many experimental and numerical studies on the impact damage problem [for example 1-9]. There are few works focusing on the multiple delaminations developing at the impact point from the fracture mechanical point of view. Suemasu et al. have analytically explained the multiple damage propagation problem in axi-symmetric plate subjected to quasi-static loading based on the fracture mechanics [6, 7]. Aoki et al. have numerically studied the stability problems of the delamination in quasi-isotropic laminates through a three-dimensional finite element analysis [8, 9].

The growth process must be considered to explain the formation of the damage in more depth. Many researchers have proposed and used various elements to study the damage growth in composite and reported their advantages and disadvantages to simulate the damage accumulation. The interface element is particularly convenient to analyze the delamination propagation because the fracture surface is prescribed [10-16]. In this paper, an interface element is proposed to simulate the delamination propagation in a three dimensional problem. This element is applied to the DCB and ENF problems to demonstrate its validity. Also, the element is applied to the problem of the growth of multiple delaminations in cross-ply laminates subjected to static transverse load.

INTERFACE ELEMENT

Interface elements of no thickness are placed between brick elements as shown in Figure 1, where delaminations are expected to propagate. The number of the nodes of the interface element is 16 when it is used between the 20-node brick elements. The coordinates x, y, z and ξ, η are global and local coordinate systems, respectively. The relative in-plane displacements $\Delta u, \Delta v$ and out-of plane displacement Δw are defined as

$$\Delta u = \sum_{i=1}^8 \phi_i(\xi, \eta) \Delta u_i, \quad \Delta v = \sum_{i=1}^8 \phi_i(\xi, \eta) \Delta v_i, \quad \Delta w = \sum_{i=1}^8 \phi_i(\xi, \eta) \Delta w_i \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta u_i = u_{i'} - u_i, \quad \Delta v_i = v_{i'} - v_i, \quad \Delta w_i = w_{i'} - w_i$$

where $\phi_i(\xi, \eta)$ is a shape function, and u_i, v_i, w_i and $u_{i'}, v_{i'}, w_{i'}$ indicate nodal displacement components at nodes i and i' , respectively. The energy stored in the element per unit area is defined to be a function of relative displacements as

$$\Phi = G_t \{1 - \exp(-\varphi)\} + f(\Delta w) \quad (2)$$

$$\varphi = \alpha \Delta w^2 + \beta (\Delta u^2 + \Delta v^2)$$

where

$$f(\Delta w) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} k_c \Delta w^2 & \Delta w < 0 \\ 0 & \Delta w \geq 0 \end{cases}$$

and where G_t is a critical total energy release rate of the interface and α and β are the coefficients to be determined to adjust the relationships between the relative displacements and the tractions. The second term of the right-hand side in Eq.2 is introduced to consider the contact problem, which can be thought a penalty function. The energy density function should be smoothly increasing function to make the finite element analysis efficient and stable. The tractions in each direction at node i are given in the following forms.

$$T_{ui} = \iint_{A_e} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \Delta u} \phi_i dA_e = \iint_{A_e} 2\beta G_t \Delta u \cdot \exp(-\varphi) \cdot \phi_i dA_e$$

$$T_{vi} = \iint_{A_e} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \Delta v} \phi_i dA_e = \iint_{A_e} 2\beta G_t \Delta v \cdot \exp(-\varphi) \cdot \phi_i dA_e \quad (3)$$

$$T_{wi} = \iint_{A_e} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \Delta w} \phi_i dA_e = \iint_{A_e} \{2\alpha G_t \Delta w \cdot \exp(-\varphi) + f'(\Delta w)\} \phi_i dA_e$$

Figure 1 Concept of interface element

where $dA_e = |J|d\xi d\eta$, $|J|$ is Jacobian and $i=1 \dots 8$. Tangent stiffness matrix \mathbf{K}_t of an element is derived by differentiating the traction vector \mathbf{T} by the nodal displacements $\Delta \mathbf{u}$ as

$$\delta \Gamma_i = \mathbf{K}_{tij} \delta \Delta u_j \quad (4)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} K_{uu,ij} &= \frac{\partial T_{ui}}{\partial u_j} = 2\beta G_t \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 (1 - 2\beta \Delta u^2) \exp(-\varphi) \phi_i \phi_j |J| d\xi d\eta \\ K_{uv,ij} &= \frac{\partial T_{ui}}{\partial v_j} = -4\beta^2 G_t \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 (\Delta u \cdot \Delta v) \exp(-\varphi) \phi_i \phi_j |J| d\xi d\eta \\ K_{uw,ij} &= \frac{\partial T_{ui}}{\partial w_j} = -4\alpha\beta G_t \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 (\Delta u \cdot \Delta w) \exp(-\varphi) \phi_i \phi_j |J| d\xi d\eta \\ K_{vv,ij} &= \frac{\partial T_{vi}}{\partial v_j} = 2\beta G_t \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 (1 - 2\beta \Delta v^2) \exp(-\varphi) \phi_i \phi_j |J| d\xi d\eta \\ K_{vw,ij} &= \frac{\partial T_{vi}}{\partial w_j} = -4\alpha\beta G_t \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 (\Delta v \cdot \Delta w) \exp(-\varphi) \phi_i \phi_j |J| d\xi d\eta \\ K_{ww,ij} &= \frac{\partial T_{wi}}{\partial w_j} = 2\alpha G_t \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 [(1 - 2\alpha \Delta w^2) \exp(-\varphi) + f''(\Delta w)] \phi_i \phi_j |J| d\xi d\eta \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The stored energy and traction are plotted against the relative displacement Δw ($\Delta u = \Delta v = 0$) in Figure 2. The traction T reaches a maximum value T_{wc} when the relative displacement is Δw_c and then decreases to zero. The relations between T_{wc} and Δw_c are adjusted by selecting the coefficients α and β . This interface element is incorporated into the commercial finite element code ABAQUS through the USER SUBROUTINE. The distribution of the traction and the deformation near the crack tip area is schematically illustrated in Figure 3. Since the neighborhood of the crack tip area deforms significantly, the element must be sufficiently small compared to the process zone.

NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF A CRACK GROWTH IN DCB AND ENF SPECIMENS

Crack propagations in a double cantilever beam (DCB) and an end notched flexure (ENF) specimens

Figure 2. Relationship between potential energy and traction.

Figure 3 Traction and displacement at the neighborhood of the crack tip

are simulated to demonstrate the validity of the present interface element. The DCB and ENF specimens with the finite element mesh and the boundary conditions are illustrated in Figure 4. Dimensions of both specimens are 150 mm × 25 mm × 4 mm. The length of an initial crack is 30 mm. Elastic properties of the material are $E_L = 142$ GPa, $E_T = 10.8$ GPa, $G_{LT} = 5.49$ GPa, $G_{TT} = 3.72$ GPa and $\nu_{LT} = 0.3$, $\nu_{TT} = 0.45$. The critical total energy release rate G_t is 400 (J/m²). Incremental iterative approach is adopted and the displacement at the loading point is increased.

(a) (b)
Figure 4. A typical finite element mesh of DCB(a) and ENF(b) specimens.

The load is plotted against crack opening displacement for DCB test in Figure 5. When the element size L is 5 mm in the x direction, the load-displacement curve oscillates significantly according to the position of the crack tip in the each finite element. When L is reduced to 1 mm, the results are well improved and the oscillation becomes acceptably small.

Figure 6 shows load-deflection curves for ENF specimen obtained through present finite element analysis. The broken lines are closed form solutions based on the beam theory. The first stage OA is a load-deflection relationship of a beam with an initial crack of length a_0 . The energy condition $G_{II} = G_c$ is satisfied along the lines A→B and B→C, where the crack propagates from the initial length to the center of the beam and from center point to the other support point, respectively. The line OD is the load displacement curve of the completely split beam. The critical relative displacement of the interface element Δu_{cr} is changed from 0.022 mm to 0.005 mm. The numerical results agree well with the theoretical one. The analysis well follows the behavior accompanying unstable crack propagation (A→B).

When the critical relative displacement is not small enough, the deformation of the interface element disturbs the load-displacement curve when no damage propagation is attained. However, the effect of the stiffness of the interface element is not noticeable in the load-displacement relation in the propagation stage.

Figure 5. Relationships between crack opening displacement and applied load for DCB specimen.

Figure 6. Relationships between center deflection and applied load for ENF specimen

DAMAGE GROWTH IN CROSS-PLY LAMINATES

Two-dimensional propagation of delaminations in cross-ply laminates subjected to a concentrated load at its center is analyzed by using the interface element. Dimensions of the laminates are 100mm×100mm×4 mm. An isotropic plate and a cross-ply laminate (0/90)_n are analyzed. Circular initial delaminations of a radius 2.5 mm is placed at its center. Owing to the symmetry, a quarter of the plate is analyzed as shown in Figure 7. Figure 8 shows relationships between the applied load and the center deflection. The propagation of delaminations occurs first at the center interlaminar plane where the energy release rate is highest [9], when it accompanies some stiffness reduction. The stiffness reduction becomes apparent when all the delaminations propagate. Since the inplane stiffness is little influenced by the delaminations,

the difference of the stiffness becomes less with the increase of the deflection.

Figure 7. Finite element mesh of the beam and boundary conditions for ENF specimen.

Figure 8 Relationships between center deflection and applied load

The growth histories of three delaminations in an isotropic plate and a cross-ply laminate are shown in Figures 9 and 10. The delaminations are almost circular for isotropic plate, while the delaminations tend to propagate in the fiber directions of the layers just below the delaminations as expected from the distribution of the energy release rate [9]. The sizes of the delaminations are slightly different from each other for the isotropic plate, while for the cross ply laminate the delamination near the loading surface is obviously small compared to the other ones.

The growth history of the seven delaminations in cross-ply laminate is shown in Figure 11. The delaminations 2-6 propagate first and both delaminations 1 and 7 near the surfaces are small at first. However, the delamination 7 grows fast to be as large as the delaminations 2-6 afterward. The delaminations tend to propagate only in the fiber directions of the layers just below. The shapes of the delaminations are compared with the distributions of the energy release rate along the circular delaminations in Figure 12. Though the delaminations tend to propagate in the direction where the energy release rate is maximum, the shapes of the delaminations propagated do not coincide with the original

distribution of the energy release rate around circular multiple delaminations. The distributions of the energy release rate at the delaminations fronts change with the growth of all the delaminations. Growth history of the damage must be considered to assess the impact damage in the laminated plates.

The coupling effect of the transverse cracks and the delaminations are considered next. The toughness for the transverse crack propagation is equal to that of the delamination. The finite element model of the damage propagation region is shown in Figure 14 and the delaminations propagated are shown in Figure 15. Transverse cracks (not illustrated here) propagate much faster than the delaminations in this case. It is because the ply thickness of 1mm is large and driving forces for the transverse cracks is thought to become large enough before the delaminations start to propagate. The damage size is slightly smaller than the case without transverse cracks.

Figure 9. Growth of multiple delaminations in an isotropic plate for three delaminations.

Figure 10 Propagation of multiple delaminations in a cross-ply laminate for three delaminations.

Figure 11 Propagation of multiple delaminations in a cross-ply laminate for seven delaminations.

CONCLUSION

We proposed an efficient interface element for crack-like damage propagation in three-dimensional problem. The convergence of the solution is smooth when the mesh size is set small enough compared to the process zone size. The present method was successfully applied to the multiple-delamination propagation problem in CFRP cross-ply laminates. In order to disclose the impact damage problem, the history of damage growth is found to be very important. The existence of the other delaminations is

essential in the formation of impact damage.

Figure 13 Comparison of the damage shape obtained with energy release rate distribution ($P= 1.04 \text{ kN}$, $d=20\text{mm}$)

Figure 14 Interface elements in the finite element mesh when modeling the growth of both the transverse cracks and delaminations.

Figure 14 Propagation of multiple delaminations when transverse cracks are considered.

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